

Deliverable D9.8

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIALS (3 | 3)

Deliverable report

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers) has been active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure the full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
D	Deliverable
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This report, titled ‘D9.5: Dissemination and communication materials (3|3)’, aims to display all DIGIECOQUARRY’s marketing items that have been produced between June 2023 and May 2024 to maximise the project’s visibility and impact.

Designing and producing supporting materials is a task undertaken by WP9: *Implementation of the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy*. One of its goals is to design, execute, monitor and evaluate all the activities related to dissemination and communication carried out within the project.

Dissemination and communication strategies and actions are the cornerstones for generating a deep impact on DEQ's results when attracting the interest of the main stakeholders and social acceptance. To ensure the impact beyond the project lifetime, WP9 closely works with another two WPs: WP7. Mechanisms for social acceptance and interaction with policymakers and WP8. Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on RM.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY’s concept.

Dissemination assets, target groups, and roles of the partners within these strategies can be seen in D9.1: *Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan*.

2 Dissemination and Communication materials

2.1 Brochures

Figure 2. Brochure: developments of DEQ.

The brochure has also been produced in French so Vicat can easily use it for its raising awareness activities:

TRAITEMENT
Automatisation du site • Capteurs et appareils • Concasseur mobile de réduction du bruit et de capture de poussière

TRANSPORT
Numérisation et surveillance des engins mobiles • Système de géoréperage dynamique

Modélisation des données des infrastructures
Intégration et planification 4D

STRATEGY ET REGROUPEMENT
Renforcer la chaîne de valeur des granulats • Sensibilisation à l'industrie extractive

INTELLIGENCE ARTIFICIELLE
Qualité des matériaux par colorimétrie • Détermination de la taille des grains • Calcul de volume des stocks • Prédiction de la production et de la consommation • Détection d'anomalies • Metaquarry

SANTE ET SECURITE
Carte des risques pour la reconnaissance des travailleurs • Scraper safety system

Intelligent Quarrying System

Figure 3. Brochure: developments of DEQ in French.

Brochure about Artificial Intelligence services:

The AI services are supported by a Digitalization framework that allows the capture of data using IoT and mobile networks, the storage of big amounts of information in any format, a big data analytics framework based on standard tools using the most advanced security technologies.

Finally, data representation can be done with almost any standard tools available in the market. In the project, POWER BI is being used to generate Dashboards.

Figure 4. AI brochure I

DIGIECOQUARRY

Artificial Intelligence Services

Like many industries, mining can benefit from the power of digitalization and artificial intelligence (AI). But less than 1% of the data produced by quarries is being used. DigiEcoQuarry aims to design, develop, and implement an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising of sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated digitalized, automatic, and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

DEQ's Digitalization Framework

OBJECTIVE

DEQ's AI services are conceived to improve mining processes from different perspectives taking always in consideration actual needs from the 5 pilots involved in the project. They are meant to help solving the following needs:

1. Material Quality determination
2. Granulometry of produced material
3. Stockpile volume calculation
4. Machinery failure detection via sound and vibration measurements
5. Production forecast and cost optimization
6. Advanced Document processing using NLP techniques

AI Services

Quality Determination

Granulometry

Stockpile Volume Calculation

Failure Detection

Metaquarry

Production forecast and Prediction

Applied AI Technologies

Data is being processed from different formats: Video, audio, sensor readings, IoT data, multimedia files, internet resources (Energy costs, meteorological data), etc.

Computer Vision solutions using different algorithms and techniques to analyze colors, shapes, volumes.

Natural Language Programming techniques to manage large amounts of data and find information in different languages.

Deep Learning and statistic analysis to predict cost values and provide insights on how to improve efficiency in the quarries.

Figure 5. AI brochure II

This general brochure has also been translated into French:

Figure 6. General brochure in French.

2.2 Posters

The already existing poster has been updated to match the new visual identity of the partners who have changed it, and it has been translated into Italian, Portuguese and French so it can be used by the pilots in their local languages.

Figure 7. English poster.

Figure 8. Italian poster.

Figure 9. Portuguese poster.

DIGIECOQUARRY
INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SUSTAINABLE
AGGREGATES SYSTEMS

Le futur des carrières

Une avancée significative dans les capacités de numérisation et d'automatisation des processus pour l'industrie des granulats.

Santé sécurité

Amélioration des conditions de santé et de sécurité pour les travailleurs, évitant ainsi leur exposition à des opérations dangereuses grâce à des processus automatisés et contrôlés.

Efficacité, Selectivité et rentabilité

Amélioration de la sélectivité et de l'efficacité des sites de granulats, augmentant ainsi la rentabilité des processus, assurant la durabilité et la viabilité opérationnelles à long terme

Impact environnemental

Maximiser la durabilité et l'efficacité des ressources en réduisant les émissions, en améliorant la gestion de l'eau tout en garantissant un approvisionnement durable de matériaux

Acceptation sociale

Une meilleure acceptation sociale à travers la communication et l'implication des décideurs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003750

Figure 10. French poster.

The following poster was designed and displayed in a conference by Chalmers University. Details about it can be read in *D9.9 Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (3|4)*.

Figure 11. DEQ poster by Chalmers.

2.3 Booth

During the [XV International Energy and Mineral Resources Congress](#), held in León (Spain) and organized by the Spanish Consejo Superior de Colegios de Ingenieros de Minas (Higher Council of Colleges of Mining Engineering) and the Colegio Oficial de Ingenieros de Minas del Centro de España (Official Association of Mining Engineers of Central Spain), ANEFA set a booth about DEQ.

Figure 12. DEQ's booth at XV International Energy and Mineral Resources Congress.

The project was very much present in this event with this stand, dissemination items such as the below-shown leaflet, and an important presence at several round tables, sessions, and expositions.

DIGIECOQUARRY's ambition is to tap the full potential of "Digital Quarries" through a significant breakthrough in process digitalisation and automation capabilities for the aggregates sector.

Figure 13. Leaflet.

2.4 Videos

During this last period, DIGIECOQUARRY has released 14 videos, all available on its YouTube channel:

Figure 14. YouTube's landing page.

- A series of interviews with the project's participants:
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kavllwrpbDQ>
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MxrzORxhxWw>
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y1NH_QVFjNY
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rol7QFe5FnY>
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CEK5xLqvswk>
- A visit to Cimpor, our Portuguese pilot site during the Consortium Meeting 2023:
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=miLOZllwZWw>
- Videos of the technologies being developed within the project, divided by topic:
 - Drilling and blasting: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ecvAqEIM_p0
 - Treatment: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T2TDV3xHuEE>
 - Transport and haulage: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y_6wOW_cnNI
 - Digital platform: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VsV1POol-aE&t=21s>
 - Environment and H&S: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VE9PeWdKMVw>
- Videos of the AI team working at Valdilecha quarry:
 - Mechanical Failure Detection: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qZbFRCGAnHM&t=19s>
 - Calculating the stockpile volume: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zr-hOsrSL7U>
- The visit of the Project Officer and the reviewer from the Commission to Valdilecha
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KSZckdOq_Ys

- Videos prepared by SIGMA and UPM-AI for the 2nd Review in Madrid about the AI services developed in the project:

Metaquarry tool demo: <https://youtu.be/jZWq-tFGphQ>

Grain size determination service: <https://youtu.be/AKYi36rL3ow>

Quality determination service: <https://youtu.be/ZCGu5AWMGkU>

Stockpile volume calculation service: <https://youtu.be/2Qe3mMz6kEc>

Anomalies detection service: <https://youtu.be/K7zbi9i35Zs>

Production and consumption forecast service: <https://youtu.be/tYm7JaDJZu8>

- Videos prepared by ASOGRAVAS for the dissemination of the DigiEcoQuarry project and its impact in Latin America

Summit of the Global Alliance of Aggregates Producers GAIN
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nsFJucbF98c>

#TheEventOfTheWeek, about the 5th International Concrete Sustainability Conference
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hG7n4JM6IGA>

#TheEventOfTheWeek, about the IV International Seminar on Mining and Mining Planning
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9aV0n-7mKv0>

This is how the IV International Mining and Mining Planning Seminar 2023 was experienced
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MnHgusgGXDO>

DigiEcoQuarry: Revolutionizing Mining with Digital Quarries
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ggDhHAM4vgc>

Transforming the Industry: Meeting in Lisbon with the General Director of ASOGRAVAS
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OPH_uT42368

2.5 Online presence

2.5.1 Website

The website is the main communication tool of the project. Thus, it is continuously fed with news and content about the project: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/>

It has been updated to match the evolution of the project. Changes are explained below.

Figure 15. New landing page of the web.

A new tab, resources, has been added. This is a space to store all the media the project produces, ranging from pictures to marketing materials.

A Flickr account has been created to better organise and post all the pictures about the attended meetings, visits to sites, etc: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/digiecoquarry/albums/>

Figure 16. Flickr albums.

A dedicated tab, alliances, has been created to share all the activities that may come out of joint initiatives with other EU-funded projects.

On the one hand, seven EU-funded projects in the field of mining have assembled Digi-Raw, a cluster formed to expand the impact of their work, streamline research, spark innovation, and build enduring partnerships.

On the other, DIGIECOQUARRY participates in another cluster named "Sustainable CRMs4EU" together with another nine EU projects.

Figure 17. Alliances tab.

In addition, a dedicated space to DEQ can be found in the webpages of some of these sister projects.

The news section always keeps up with the project, releasing a couple of news a month.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/#news>

Figure 18. News section.

Finally, to give maximum diffusion to the Consortium Meeting held in November in Lisbon, a specific minisite was created on the website containing a summary of the meeting, pictures of each of the teams and the meeting itself and a video and photos of the visit to Cimpor's quarry.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/consortium-meeting-lisbon/>

Figure 19. Minisite about the Consortium Meeting.

More information about DEQ's website can be found in D9.2: DIGIECOQUARRY's website.

2.5.2 Social Media

Keeping DEQ’s social media profiles updated is key to attract the public’s interest and feedback and build relationships with external stakeholders. On the other hand, it helps DEQ’s D&C team to engage with the audience and find out what people are saying about the project. Due to this, profiles are frequently fed with posts related to a wide variety of topics, ranging from the project itself to raw materials-related content, EU news, etc.

DIGIECOQUARRY’s current number of followers and social media profiles are:

LinkedIn: 679

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiecoquarry>

Instagram: 229

<https://www.instagram.com/digiecoquarry/>

Twitter: 238

https://twitter.com/digi_eco

Facebook: 62

<https://www.facebook.com/Digiecoquarry>

YouTube: 33

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOC0k6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>

This adds up to a total of 1241 out of the 1000 stated in the Grant Agreement, thus surpassing this KPI.

As it can be seen, DEQ’s most followed social network is LinkedIn. Figure 20 shows last year’s statistics. The posts achieved nearly 1000 reactions and the profile was visualized around 1,200 times, achieving maximum audience during the Consortium meeting in November.

Figure 20. LinkedIn figures.

3 Conclusions

This document, titled “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities”, showcases the supporting means produced, videos recorded and edited, website updates and social media status between months 25 to 36 to help disseminate DIGIECOQUARRY at different events and situations.

Previously released items can be found in *D9.3 Dissemination and Communication materials (1|3)* and *D9.5 Dissemination and Communication materials (2|3)*.

4 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.
- D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCEP).

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